

Detecting Malicious URLs Using Classification Algorithms in Machine Learning and Deep Learning

اكتشاف محددات الموارد الضارة باستخدام خوارزميات التصنيف في التعلم الآلي والتعلم العميق

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ABSTRACT

Due to the daily necessity of using links and websites and the high prevalence of malicious URLs, many security threats arise for Internet users and organizations. These threats can lead to data breaches and identity theft, and they can cause a complete system collapse. Traditional methods of detecting malicious URLs are often insufficient and require advanced technologies. This study presents an improvement in the accuracy and speed of detecting malicious URLs through ensemble learning techniques, specifically Bagging (Bootstrap) and Stacking. Extensive experiments on a large, balanced dataset containing 491,530 URLs, equally distributed between benign and malicious, showed that ensemble learning models significantly outperform other algorithms. The Bagging classifier, which uses decision trees as the base classifier, achieved an accuracy of 99.01%, a training time of 23.84 seconds, and a prediction time of 0.86 seconds. The Stacking classifier, which uses AdaBoost, Random Forest, and XGBoost as base classifiers, also achieved similar results, although the training time increased to 199.6944 seconds due to the complexity of this model. In addition to the results, we obtained, which demonstrated the superiority of bagging and stacking models, we conducted a comprehensive comparison with other popular models, ranging from individual machine learning models such as k-Nearest Neighbors, to deep learning models such as feedforward neural networks, to ensemble learning models with various techniques such as boosting. These results highlight the promising potential of ensemble learning in strengthening cybersecurity measures and protecting users and businesses from malicious URL attacks.

Keywords: Uniform Resource Locator (URLs), Supervised Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Ensemble Learning, Cybersecurity, Classification Algorithms, Benign URLs, Malicious URLs.

المخلص

بسبب الحاجة اليومية لاستخدام الروابط ومواقع الويب، وانتشار عناوين URL الضارة، تنشأ تهديدات أمنية كثيرة لمستخدمي الإنترنت والمؤسسات. يمكن أن تؤدي هذه التهديدات إلى خروقات للبيانات وسرقة الهوية، وقد تتسبب في انهيار النظام بالكامل. غالباً ما تكون الطرق التقليدية لاكتشاف عناوين URL الضارة غير كافية وتتطلب تقنيات متقدمة. تقدم هذه الدراسة تحسناً في دقة وسرعة اكتشاف العناوين الضارة من خلال استخدام تقنيات التعلم التجميعي، وتحديدًا تقنيتي التعبئة والتكديس. أظهرت التجارب المكثفة التي أجريت على مجموعة بيانات كبيرة ومتوازنة تحتوي على 491,530 عنواناً، موزعة بالتساوي بين الحميدة والضارة، أن نماذج التعلم التجميعي

تتفوق تفوقاً كبيراً على الخوارزميات الأخرى. حقق مصنف التعبئة الذي يستخدم أشجار القرار كمصنف أساسي دقة بنسبة 99.01%، وزمن تدريب قدره 23.84 ثانية، وزمن تنبؤ قدره 0.86 ثانية. كما حقق مُصنّف التكدس الذي يضم مصنف التعزيز التكراري (AdaBoost) ومصنف الغابة العشوائية (Random Forest) ومصنف التعزيز التدريجي الفائق (XGBoost) كمُصنّفات أساسية نتائج مماثلة، على الرغم من زيادة زمن التدريب إلى 199.6944 ثانية نظراً لتعقيد هذا النموذج. بالإضافة إلى النتائج التي حصلنا عليها، والتي أظهرت تفوق نماذج التجميع والتكدس، أجرينا مقارنة شاملة مع نماذج شائعة أخرى، بدءاً من نماذج التعلم الآلي الفردية مثل نموذج أقرب الجيران (k-Nearest Neighbors) ووصولاً إلى نماذج التعلم العميق مثل الشبكات العصبية ذات التغذية الأمامية (Feedforward Neural Networks)، ووصولاً إلى نماذج التعلم التجميعي باستخدام تقنيات متنوعة مثل التعزيز (Boosting). تُسلط هذه النتائج الضوء على الإمكانيات الواعدة للتعلم التجميعي في تعزيز تدابير الأمن السيبراني وحماية المستخدمين والشركات من هجمات العناوين الضارة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: محددات مواقع الموارد الموحدة (URLs)، التعلم الآلي الخاضع للإشراف، التعلم العميق، التعلم التجميعي، الأمن السيبراني، خوارزميات التصنيف، العناوين الحميدة، العناوين الضارة.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet has become an indispensable part of modern life, providing access to information on an unprecedented scale. However, this digital landscape also presents an increasing number of security risks, including the proliferation of malicious URLs, often hidden within emails, social media posts, and malicious website browsing experiences. When a user accidentally clicks on a malicious URL, it can cause a variety of damage to both the user and the organization. These URLs can redirect users to phishing sites that cybercriminals have carefully designed to look like legitimate sites, such as banks, online retailers, or government agencies. These phishing sites aim to trick users into voluntarily divulging sensitive information, including usernames, passwords, credit card numbers, Social Security numbers, and other important personal data, which can result in serious damage such as financial loss and the use of the data to defraud others (1). The continued development of phishing sites, which often use advanced social engineering techniques, increases the risk of exploiting users' trust despite their security awareness training (2). Malicious URLs are one of the most common ways malware spreads. A single click

on a malicious URL can trigger the download a installation of a wide range of malware, including viruses, Trojans, ransomware, spyware, and keyloggers without the user noticing (3). These malicious programs can compromise the user's device, steal data, encrypt files and demand a ransom to decrypt them, monitor user activity, or even give attackers complete remote control over the device on which the malware is installed. Ultimately, this can cause financial, operational, or reputational damage to companies and organizations that hold user data (4). Traditional methods, such as blacklisting, fail to effectively identify newly emerging threats to detect malicious URLs, as these methods rely on pre-defined malicious URLs, leaving a gap in protection against unknown or newly created malicious links. Attackers are constantly working to circumvent blacklists by constantly creating new URLs and using techniques such as URL shortening and domain spoofing (creating domains that visually resemble legitimate ones) (5). Furthermore, attackers use sophisticated social engineering techniques, crafting convincing messages and deceptive links that exploit human psychology to lure users into clicking and effectively bypass many technical defenses

(6). Whitelisting, an alternative approach to blacklisting where only pre-approved URLs are allowed, severely restricts user access and is often impractical for general Internet use. Machine learning has emerged as a powerful tool in the field of cybersecurity, providing more dynamic and efficient solutions to address these sophisticated threats by harnessing the power of data analysis. Machine learning algorithms can learn patterns and characteristics associated with malicious URLs, enabling them to accurately classify unknown URLs (7). Unlike traditional systems, machine learning models can adapt to new URL patterns and identify previously unseen threats, making them a critical component of proactive cybersecurity protection. Deep learning enhances this capability further by detecting subtle indicators of maliciousness (8) that traditional methods or even simple machine learning approaches may miss. Despite the accuracy that deep learning models may provide, they require more time in the detection process, prompting us to consider a way to combine the speed of traditional machine learning models with the accuracy of deep learning models (9,10). This leads us to explore ensemble models. This research focuses on exploring the effectiveness of machine learning and deep learning techniques for detecting malicious URLs, specifically investigating the potential of ensemble learning methods to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of detection. We aim to contribute to the advancement of cybersecurity by:

- Analyzing the essential components and features of URLs: Extracting the essential lexical features that distinguish benign from malicious URLs. This will include a deep dive into the structural elements of URLs and an exploration of how features such as URL length, character distribution, presence of specific keywords, and domain characteristics can be used to identify potentially malicious URLs.

- Investigating the performance of various classification algorithms: Discovering the most efficient models for URL classification. This will include a comparative analysis of different machine learning algorithms, including both traditional methods (e.g., support vector machines and naive Bayes) and more advanced deep learning methods (e.g., convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks). The goal is to identify the algorithms that are best suited to the specific task of detecting malicious URLs, taking into account factors such as accuracy and speed.
- Proposing and testing ensemble learning techniques: Exploring the benefits of combining multiple models to improve accuracy and reduce training time. Ensemble techniques such as bagging and stacking offer the potential to leverage the strengths of different individual models, creating a more robust and accurate detection method overall.

This research specifically investigates the effectiveness of clustering techniques, especially bagging and stacking, in the context of detecting malicious URLs. First, we extract and analyze lexical features from the dataset, pre-process the data, and then compare the performance of several classification algorithms, including traditional machine learning models, deep learning, and ensemble learning. Finally, we evaluate the effectiveness of bagging and stacking techniques, highlighting their potential to enhance detection capabilities and reduce training and testing time, thus enhancing cybersecurity measures against malicious URL threats. Detecting malicious URLs has been an important focus of cybersecurity research, with many studies exploring a wide range of machine learning, deep learning, and ensemble methods. These efforts can be categorized based on the approach used to detect malicious URLs.

Machine Learning Classifiers

The basic approach involves applying traditional machine learning classifiers. Xuan et al. (11) investigated the use of support vector machines (SVM) and random forests (RF) to distinguish malicious URLs. Their dataset included 470,000 URLs, using an imbalanced dataset (400,000 benign and 70,000 malicious). While the random forest showed superior predictive effectiveness, the training time was quite long. However, the testing time was similar. Vardhan et al. (12) performed a comparative analysis of several supervised machine learning algorithms. These included naive Bayes, k-nearest neighbors (KNN), stochastic gradient descent, logistic regression, decision trees, and random forest. They used a dataset of 450,000 URLs obtained from Kaggle. Of these, the random forest consistently achieved the highest accuracy. However, a major limitation identified was the high computational cost associated with the random forest, which hinders its deployment in real-time applications. Awodiji (13) focused his research on mitigating threats such as malware, phishing, and spam by applying SVM, naive Bayes, decision trees, and random forests. For training and evaluation, he used the ISCX-URL-2016 dataset from the University of New Brunswick, known for its diverse representation of malicious URL types. The random forest algorithm achieved the best accuracy (98.8%), outperforming the other algorithms. However, the study lacks specific details regarding the training time and computational resource requirements of each algorithm, making it difficult to evaluate their overall efficiency. Velpula (14) proposed a random forest-based machine learning model that combined lexical, host-based, and content-based features. This approach leveraged a dataset from the University of California, Irvine, Machine Learning Repository containing 11,000 phishing URLs. The dataset was rich in features, including static features (e.g., domain age and URL length) and dynamic features (e.g., number of exemplars and

external links). While the combination of diverse features significantly improved the model's accuracy to 97%, the research did not explore the potential of other machine learning algorithms. Reyes-Dorta et al. (15) explored the relatively new field of quantum machine learning (QML) for detecting malicious URLs and compared its effectiveness with classical machine learning techniques. They used the "Hidden Phishing URL Dataset," which included 185,180 URLs. Their results showed that traditional machine learning methods, especially SVM with Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel, achieved high accuracy levels (above 90%). The research also highlighted the effectiveness of neural networks but noted that the current limitations of quantum hardware hinder the widespread application of QML in this field, making traditional machine learning models perform better due to their continuous improvement.

Deep Learning Models

Deep learning, with its ability to learn complex patterns from data, has emerged as a promising approach for detecting malicious URLs. Johnson et al. (16) conducted a comparative study of traditional machine learning algorithms (RF, C4.5, KNN) and deep learning models (GRU, LSTM, CNN). Their study confirmed the importance of lexical features for detecting malicious URLs, using the ISCX-URL-2016 dataset. The results indicated that the GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) deep learning model outperformed the Random Forest algorithm. However, the researchers did not compare them with other machine learning and deep learning algorithms to explore whether they achieve better accuracy. Aljabri et al. (17) evaluated the performance of both machine learning models (Naive Bayes, Random Forest) and deep learning models (CNN, LSTM) in the context of detecting malicious URLs. The researchers used a large, imbalanced dataset obtained by web crawling with Mal Crawler. 1.2 million URLs were used for training, of which 27,253 were considered

malicious, 1,172,747 were considered benign, and 0.364 million URLs were used for testing. The dataset was validated using Google's Safe Browsing API. The results showed that the Naive Bayes model achieved the highest accuracy (96%). However, the study had limitations, including unexplored potential of other machine learning and deep learning algorithms, and uneven distribution within the dataset. These limitations may limit the generalizability of the results and potentially introduce bias into the model. Gopali et al. (18) proposed a new approach by treating URLs as sequences of symbols, enabling the application of deep learning algorithms designed for sequence processing, such as TCN (Temporal Convolutional Network), LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory), BiLSTM (Bidirectional LSTM), and multi-head attention. The study specifically emphasized the important role of contextual features within URLs for effective phishing detection. Their results confirmed that the proposed deep learning models, particularly BiLSTM and multi-head attention, were more accurate than other methods such as random forests. However, the study used a specialized dataset, limiting the generalizability of the results to other URL datasets, and did not comprehensively evaluate a broader range of other deep learning and machine learning algorithms.

Ensemble Learning Approaches

In addition to single classifiers, ensemble approaches, which combine multiple models, have been explored to improve detection performance. Chen et al. (19) leveraged the XGBoost algorithm, a boosting algorithm. Boosting is a popular ensemble learning technique known for its classification speed. Their work emphasized the importance of lexical features in identifying malicious URLs. Through feature selection, they initially identified 17 potentially important features, and then refined them to the nine best features to reduce model complexity while maintaining a high accuracy of 99.93%. However, the study

did not provide a sufficiently detailed description of the required training time and computational resources consumed by the XGBoost model.

Feature Engineering and Selection

Recognizing the importance of feature quality to model performance, some research has focused specifically on feature engineering and selection techniques. Oshingbesan et al. (20) sought to improve malicious URL recognition by applying machine learning with a strong focus on feature engineering. Their approach involved the use of 78 lexical features, including hostname length, top-level domain, and the number of paths in a URL. Furthermore, they introduced new features called "benign score" and "malicious score," derived using linguistic modeling techniques. The study evaluated ten different machine learning and deep learning models: KNN, random forest, decision trees, logistic regression, support vector machines (SVM), linear support vector machines (SVM), feed-forward neural networks (FFNN), naive Bayes, K-Means, and Gaussian mixture models (GMM). Although the K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) algorithm achieved the highest accuracy, it suffers from significant drawbacks in terms of training and prediction time requirements. Mat Rani et al. (21) emphasized the critical role of selecting effective features for classifying malicious URLs. They used information acquisition and tree-shape techniques to improve the performance of machine learning models, particularly in the context of phishing site detection. The study used three classifiers: Naive Bayes, Random Forest, and XGBoost. Features selected using the tree-shape technique showed a significant positive impact on accuracy. While XGBoost achieved the highest accuracy of 98.59%, the study did not fully explore the potential of other deep learning algorithms or delve into aspects of model efficiency, such as their speed and resource requirements during the training and testing phases. Even though machine learning and deep learning methods have achieved high

accuracy in identifying malicious URLs, there are concerns regarding training and prediction time efficiency and the complexity of tuning hyperparameters (11–21). Ensemble methods, such as Random Forest and XGBoost, are effective due to their ability to handle high-dimensional data, improve accuracy, and reduce the overfitting problem. However, they often require higher computational requirements (20), (21). Despite the great efforts made by researchers to detect malicious URLs, critical analysis reveals several points that need to be explored and require further attention.

- **Real-Time Applications:** Most studies have focused on achieving high accuracy but do not delve into time efficiency, which is critical for detecting malicious URLs, especially in light of the rapid technological development.

This limitation raises concerns about the feasibility of using these models in real-time applications (11–21).

- **Data Imbalance:** Most research on datasets suffers from an imbalance between benign and malicious URLs (11–21). This imbalance significantly impacts model training and may bias the model's performance in favor of the dominant class. Techniques such as over-sampling and under-sampling are needed to address this issue for more reliable evaluation.
- **Feature Extraction and Selection:** Some research shows the need to explore how features are extracted, transformed, and selected effectively to improve training and prediction, efficiency, and accuracy(14,17,19–21).

Table 1: Related works summary

Author(s)	Models	Datasets	Advantages	Limitations
Xuan et al. (11) (2020)	SVM, RF	Undisclosed, approx. 470,000 URLs	Novel feature set proposed.	Lacks detail, algorithm optimization is unclear, and dataset specifics are sparse.
Vardhan et al. (12) (2023)	LR, SGD, RF, SVM, NB, KNN, DT	Approx. 450,000 URLs (Kaggle)	Evaluate multiple ML algorithms. Straightforward methodology.	Lacks detail on preprocessing and class imbalance. Feature selection was not discussed.
Chen et al. (19) (2020)	XGBoost (post feature selection)	Size and source are not clearly defined	Introduces new features. High accuracy.	Dataset specifics are lacking. Unclear obfuscation feature extraction. Insufficient validation detail.
Mat Rani et al. (21) (2023)	Naïve Bayes, RF, XGBoost	ISCX-URL-2016, Hannousse & Yahiouche (2020)	Systematic feature selection (Information gain, TreeSHAP). Improved efficiency.	Limited dataset details. Unclear comparisons between methods. Limited generalizability.
Awodiji (13) (2022)	RF, DT, NB, SVM	ISCX-URL-2016	Comprehensive ML model comparison on a public dataset. Relatively straightforward.	Lacks data preprocessing and feature selection. The detailed conclusion overstates comprehensiveness. Class imbalance not addressed.
Johnson et al. (16) (2020)	RF, CART, KNN	ISCX-URL-2016	Deep learning and traditional ML	Dataset-specific results.

			comparison across architectures. High accuracy.	Limited hyperparameter details. Generalizability is unclear.
Oshingbesan et al. (20) (2020)	KNN, RF, DT, LR, SVM, NB, AdaBoost, GB, Extra Trees	Size and source are not clearly defined	Investigate model generalization across multiple datasets. Baseline comparison.	Lacks dataset specifics. Unclear data preprocessing and feature extraction. Insufficient performance analysis.
Aljabri et al. (17) (2022)	NB, RF, CNN, LSTM	million 1.2 URLs for training million 0.364 for testing (web crawling)	Thorough feature engineering. Compares ML/DL algorithms. Uses multiple feature selection methods.	The dataset source is unclear. Limited feature engineering details. Potentially imbalanced data.
Velpula (14) (2023)	Random Forest	Approx. 11,000+ phishing websites (UCI)	Addresses class imbalance using SMOTE. Multiple feature types. Straightforward methodology.	Dataset details are limited. The feature extraction detail is lacking. Slow prediction.
Reyes-Dorta et al. (15) (2024)	LR, NB, SVM, DT, CNN, QML algorithms	Hidden Fraudulent URLs dataset	Compares classical ML with QML. High true positive rates. Innovation with QML applications.	Categorical variable encoding details are missing. Limited quantum generalizability. Data preprocessing needs further detailing.
Gopali et al. (18) (2024)	Multi-Head Attention, TCN, BiLSTM, LSTM, DQN	Approx. 73,575 URLs (GitHub)	Novel sequential approach. Compares deep learning models. Includes run-time assessment for efficiency	Limited dataset details. Potential class imbalance not addressed.

METHODOLOGY

Hardware Specifications

The experiments in this research were conducted using Google Colaboratory (Colab) with virtual CPU settings to ensure methodological consistency. Colab operates on a dynamic resource allocation model, and the predominant configuration consists of an Intel Xeon processor with two virtual central processing units (vCPUs) and 13 GB of RAM. Acknowledging that there is potential for slight inter-session variations in resource assignment.

Dataset

The dataset (benign and malicious URLs) (22) used in this research consists of 632,508 rows

with an equal distribution of 316,254 benign URLs and 316,254 malicious URLs, categorized according to the three columns, “url”, “label”, and “result”, which contain the URL itself, the corresponding classification label (either ‘Benign’ or ‘Malicious’), and the classification result as an integer value (0 for benign and 1 for malicious), We extracted a total of 27 lexical features from each URL as shown in Table 2.

Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is critical to achieving reliable and accurate results, as missing values and inconsistencies can introduce significant bias during the training process, leading to inaccurate predictions. Preprocessing steps,

such as cleaning, integration, transformation, and normalization, improve model performance and prevent overfitting by ensuring data consistency and representation.

NO.	Feature	Data type	Description
1	url_length	int64	Title length
2	url_scheme	object	Protocol type (http https ftp)
3	path_length	int64	Path length
4	ip_present	int64	Is an explicit IP address used?
5	number_of_digits	int64	Number of digits in the address
6	number_of_parameters	int64	Number of parameters in the address (= separates the key and the parameter value)
7	number_of_fragments	int64	Number of parts in the title (parts start with a #)
8	is_url_encoded	bool	Does the address contain non-ASCII characters (characters are encoded using a % sign followed by hexadecimal digits)?
9	number_encoded_char	int64	Number of characters encoded
10	number_of_subdirectories	int64	Number of subdirectories
11	host_length	int64	Hostname length
12	has_client	bool	Does the title contain the word "client" or not?
13	has_admin	bool	Does the title contain the word "admin" or not?
14	has_server	bool	Does the title contain the word "server" or not?
15	has_login	bool	Does the title contain the word "login" or not?
16	number_of_dashes	int64	Number of hyphens (-) in the domain name
17	has_at_sign	bool	Does the address contain an at sign (@) or not?
18	is_tiny_url	int64	Is the title short or not?
19	get_tld	object	Top level domain like (com org edu ..)
20	number_of_subdomains_and_extensions	int64	Total number of subdomains and extensions
21	number_of_spaces	int64	Number of blank spaces in the title
22	number_of_zeros	int64	Number of zeros in the address
23	is_url_single_character_directory	int64	Does the title contain a single character in the directory or not?
24	number_of_uppercase	int64	Number of capital letters in the title
25	number_of_lowercase	int64	Number of lowercase letters in the title
26	ratio_upper_to_lower	float64	ratio of uppercase letters to lowercase letters
27	number_of_double_slashes	int64	Number of punctuation marks (//) in the title

Data Cleaning

The missing values (NaN) and inconsistent data within the dataset are removed, ensuring its completeness and accuracy to train the model reliably. After the deletion process, the dataset became unbalanced. To overcome this problem

and rebalance the dataset, the Random Under Sampling technique was used, where samples from the majority class were randomly deleted. The resulting balanced dataset was saved to complete other pre-processing steps on it. Figure 1 shows the balanced distribution of samples:

Fig 1. Distribution of URLs after applying the Random Under Sampling technique to balance the samples

Data Integrity

Maintaining a consistent data structure by standardizing column names and data formats requires ensuring the dataset does not contain duplicates or inconsistencies in the format of different attributes.

Data Transformation

Converting categorical features such as url_scheme and get_tld into a numeric format, which can be easily processed by various machine learning algorithms. This involved converting categorical variables into multiple numeric variables. The url_scheme feature was converted into four features, each representing

a single protocol. We got four new features as shown in Table 3. The top-level domain feature (get_tld), which is a categorical feature, was converted using an ordinal encoder to be processed by the algorithms(23).

Data Normalization

Normalizing the data's numeric attributes was conducted using appropriate techniques. Features such as url_length, path_length, and host length were normalized to achieve better model performance by equalizing the impact of these attributes, which differ in magnitude.

NO.	Feature	Data Type	Description
1	url_scheme_ftp	int64	Whether the URL uses the FTP protocol or not.
2	url_scheme_http	int64	Whether the URL uses the HTTP protocol or not.
3	url_scheme_https	int64	Whether the URL uses the HTTP protocol or not.
4	url_scheme_https	int64	Whether the URL contains the term https

Feature Selection

Correlation-based feature selection was used to examine the relationship between features and the target variable. This method is characterized by its rapid feature selection while maintaining classification accuracy. The most influential features that had significant correlations with the target variable and small correlations between them were then selected

to reduce redundancy and simplify model building (24,25). After selecting the features that were most correlated with the target variable ['result'], thirteen independent variables (features) were selected, as shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the data preparation process, illustrating all the steps taken to obtain a balanced dataset.

Fig 2. The lexical features most correlated to the dependent variable (result)

Fig 3. Data preparation process

Proposed Solution

This study proposes an innovative approach to detecting malicious URLs using ensemble learning techniques, specifically Bagging (Bootstrap aggregation) and stacking. Bagging (Bootstrap aggregation) uses 50 decision trees as its baseline models, yielding better results than using more or fewer trees, as shown in Tables 9 and 10. Majority voting is used to obtain the final predictions, as shown in Figure 4. While stacking uses models (AdaBoost, Random Forest, and XGBoost) as base models and uses a random forest as meta model to obtain the final predictions, as shown in Figure 5. These techniques combine predictions from multiple base learners, resulting in a faster and more accurate classification model. Bagging is a statistical procedure that creates multiple datasets by sampling the data with replacement to obtain a final prediction result with minimal variance(26). Stacking combines weak learners to create a strong learner. It combines heterogeneous parallel models to reduce bias in these models. Stacking is also known as stacked generalization. Similar to averaging, all models (weak learners) contribute based on their weights and performance, to build a new model on top of the others(27). Models (AdaBoost, Random Forest, and XGBoost) were used as weak learners to gain different perspectives on the dataset and avoid duplicate predictions.

Fig 4. Proposed bagging model

Fig 5. Proposed stacking model

Verifying the Results

To analyze the effectiveness of the proposed solution extensively, a comparison of its performance with many traditional machine learning algorithms and deep learning techniques is applied. The algorithms that were implemented and evaluated include:

Traditional Machine Learning Algorithms

The machine learning algorithms evaluated included several with specific parameter settings. The Decision Tree was configured with `random_state=42` for consistent results. Logistic Regression used `max_iter=5000` and `random_state=42`. The SVM was trained with a linear kernel (`kernel='linear'`) and `random_state=42`. Finally, K-Nearest Neighbors was set to consider 3 neighbors (`n_neighbors=3`). Gaussian Naive Bayes and Bernoulli Naive Bayes were used with default parameter settings without adjustments.

Deep Learning Algorithms

The deep learning models, CNN, FFNN and RNN are set using various parameters to adjust the model's performance. The CNN has several convolutional layers and max-pooling layers, a

flatten layer, and two Dense layers. The FFNN had set Adam as the model optimizer, has an initial learning rate of 0.001, each layer having different number of parameters. The FFNN had three Dense Layers. RNN has two Simple RNN layers and also uses Adam. Finally, the Radial Basis Function Network has set `hidden_layer_sizes= (10)`, the maximum iterations are set to 1000 iterations.

Ensemble Learning Algorithms

The ensemble learning algorithms employed a variety of configurations to create robust predictive models. The initial Voting Classifier was set to use a hard voting strategy. The initial Stacking Classifier integrated a Decision Tree Classifier with `random_state=42` as its final estimator, utilized all available cores (`n_jobs=-1`), and employed `passthrough`. Bagging Classifiers were configured with 50 base estimators (`n_estimators=50`), a Decision Tree Classifier (with the default random state) as the base estimator, a `max_samples` value of 0.80, specified bootstrap sampling, and a `random_state` of 42. AdaBoost used 100 estimators (`n_estimators=100`), a Decision Tree Classifier with `max_depth=10` as the base estimator, a learning rate of 0.5, and `random_state=42`. The final Voting and Stacking classifiers were then set up in the same way. Gradient Boosting and Extra Trees utilized a fixed `random_state`.

Model Evaluation

To evaluate model performance, we employed a comprehensive set of metrics, including:

- Confusion Matrix: Table 4 shows the confusion matrix, which compares predicted classifications to actual labels, revealing True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN). This is crucial for binary classification tasks.
- Accuracy: Overall correct predictions.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

- Precision: Correctly predicted malicious URLs out of all those predicted as malicious, where high precision minimizes false positives.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (2)$$

- Recall: Correctly identified malicious URLs out of all actual malicious URLs, where high recall minimizes false negatives.

$$Recall \mid TPR \mid Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3)$$

- Specificity: Correctly identified benign URLs out of all actual benign URLs.

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (4)$$

- F1 Score: Harmonic mean of precision and recall.

$$F1 \text{ Score} = \frac{2*Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall} \quad (5)$$

Table 4: Confusion matrix		
	Predicted Positive (Malicious)	Predicted Negative (Benign)
Actual Positive (Malicious)	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
Actual Negative (Benign)	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

Training and Prediction Time

- Training Time: Training time measures the time taken to train each model on the training data, providing insights into the efficiency and scalability of different learning algorithms.
- Prediction Time: Prediction time quantifies the time required for each trained model to predict the classification of a new URL and assesses the model’s suitability for online URL filtering applications that require fast responses to incoming URLs, impacting the model’s applicability in real-time systems. In this paper, we calculated the above metrics for each of the algorithms considered in our research, resulting in a comparative performance analysis that reported on the selection of the optimal model.

RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained from the implemented algorithms, discusses their performance, and compares their strengths and limitations. To evaluate the models, we focus on accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, F1 score, training time, and prediction time for each model to provide a comprehensive analysis of their effectiveness in detecting malicious URLs.

Individual Machine Learning Models

Tables 5 and 6 summarize the performance of six common machine learning algorithms, namely K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Classifier (SVC), Gaussian Naive Bayes, and Bernoulli Naive Bayes, evaluated based on several key metrics to provide a clear picture of their performance in classifying URLs as benign or malicious. Based on the results of practical experiments on individual machine-learning models, we summarize the following:

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model achieved the highest accuracy, reaching 98.94%, while the Bernoulli Naive Bayes (Bernoulli NB) model exhibited the lowest accuracy at 96.27%. Drilling down into individual metrics, Bernoulli NB demonstrated exceptional precision of 0.999, effectively identifying benign URLs. However, the Decision Tree model excelled in recall 0.985, successfully identifying malicious URLs. Bernoulli NB also showed the best specificity. Finally, KNN displayed the best-balanced performance, as measured by the F1 score, which considers both precision and recall. The models also varied significantly in terms of speed. Bernoulli NB was the quickest in training at 0.126

seconds, whereas the Support Vector Machine (SVC) model required substantially more time 17 minutes, possibly due to the size of the dataset used for training and model optimization. For prediction, Logistic Regression outperformed all others, whereas KNN had the longest prediction times. These

results illustrate a crucial tradeoff between computational efficiency and predictive power, where simple and easily trained models require less computational overhead, whilst algorithms that model complex non-linear patterns typically require a considerably greater level of computing time.

Table 5: Evaluation metrics results for individual machine learning models

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	Specificity	F1 Score
K-Neighbors Classifier	98.94	0.994	0.984	0.994	0.989
Decision Tree Classifier	98.68	0.988	0.985	0.988	0.986
Logistic Regression	98.05	0.995	0.965	0.995	0.980
SVC	97.85	0.998	0.958	0.998	0.978
Gaussian NB	96.38	0.999	0.928	0.999	0.962
Bernoulli NB	96.27	0.999	0.925	0.999	0.961

Table 6: Training and prediction time for individual machine learning models

Classifier	Training time (Sec)	Validation set prediction time (Sec)	Test set prediction time (Sec)
K-Neighbors Classifier	0.859	129.793	107.913
Decision Tree Classifier	0.788	0.018	0.017
Logistic Regression	24.217	0.015	0.013
SVC	1027.56	67.390	57.12
Gaussian NB	0.139	0.028	0.022
Bernoulli NB	0.126	0.044	0.036

Deep Learning Models

Table 7 presents the performance metrics for four prominent deep learning models FFNN (Feed Forward Neural Network), CNN (Convolutional Neural Network), RNN (Recurrent Neural Network), and RBFN (Radial Basis Function Network), while Table 8 shows the time each model took to train and predict. Based on the results of practical experiments on deep learning models, we concluded the following: The Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) achieved the highest accuracy at

98.64%, while the Radial Basis Function Network (RBFN) had the lowest accuracy at 98.52%. While the accuracy differences were small, other metrics showed some variation; the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) showed the highest precision and specificity, indicating its ability to correctly identify both benign and malicious URLs, whereas the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) achieved the highest recall, showing high effectiveness in capturing actual malicious URLs, despite it only showing the second highest accuracy level.

Ultimately, the FFNN model exhibited the highest F1 score. Regarding speed, the RBFN model proved to be the most computationally efficient in terms of training time, completing the training process in 33.189 seconds,

compared to the CNN, which required over 10 times longer. It is noteworthy to remember the significantly increased computational power required for the CNN. Furthermore, RBFN was also the fastest model for making predictions.

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	Specificity	F1 Score
FFNN	98.64	0.996	0.976	0.996	0.986
CNN	98.62	0.996	0.975	0.996	0.986
RNN	98.54	0.991	0.978	0.992	0.985
RBFN	98.52	0.995	0.975	0.995	0.985

Classifier	Training Time (Sec)	Validation set prediction time (Sec)	Test set prediction time (Sec)
FFNN	238.709	6.998	5.162
CNN	366.821	7.933	10.282
RNN	355.990	10.057	9.304
RBFN	33.189	0.034	0.029

Ensemble Learning Models

Tables 9 and 10 show the performance of twelve ensemble learning models using their three techniques (bagging, stacking, and boosting). Regarding experiments on ensemble learning models, we note the following:

Bagging (bootstrap) is the top performer in terms of accuracy, reaching 99.01%. At the other end of the spectrum, the stacking model combining Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, and Naive Bayes showed the lowest accuracy. Examining other key metrics, the Voting model incorporating Adaboost, Random Forest, and XGBoost models achieved both the highest precision and specificity. Interestingly, Bagging (pasting), a variation of the Bagging algorithm, demonstrated the highest recall. For the best-balanced performance, reflected in the F1-score, stacking combining Adaboost, Random Forest, and XGBoost produced the highest F1-

score. The speed varied substantially across the different ensemble techniques investigated. In the training process, the individual XGBoost model was significantly faster. In contrast, the Stacking model incorporating Adaboost, Random Forest, and XGBoost, was by far the slowest to train. For prediction speed, the stacking model (Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes) demonstrated speed during prediction. The slowest prediction time, unsurprisingly, was seen with Stacking (Adaboost, Random Forest, and XGBoost), confirming that the complexity incurred through higher-level models impacts both training and testing times within the model.

A comprehensive performance evaluation of all models highlights notable differences in strengths and weaknesses. Figure 6 provides a comparison of the overall accuracy achieved by each model, while Figures 7, 8, 9, and 10

visualize other critical metrics of model evaluation: precision, recall, specificity, and F1 score, respectively.

Table 9: Evaluation Metrics Results for Ensemble Learning Models

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	Specificity	F1 Score
Bagging (bootstrap) 10 trees	98.96	0.995	0.984	0.995	0.99
Bagging (bootstrap) 20 trees	98.99	0.995	0.985	0.995	0.99
Bagging (bootstrap) 50 trees	99.01	0.995	0.985	0.995	0.99
Bagging (bootstrap) 200 trees	99.01	0.995	0.985	0.995	0.99
Bagging (bootstrap) 500 trees	99	0.995	0.985	0.995	0.99
Stacking (ADA_RF_XGB)	99.01	0.9955	0.9847	0.9956	0.9901
Random Forest Classifier	98.99	0.9953	0.9845	0.9954	0.9899
Extra Trees Classifier	98.99	0.9953	0.9845	0.9954	0.9899
Voting (ADA_RF_XGB)	98.96	0.9979	0.9812	0.998	0.9895
XGB Classifier	98.94	0.997	0.9817	0.9971	0.9893
Cat-Boost Classifier	98.92	0.9976	0.9807	0.9976	0.989
Bagging (pasting)	98.89	0.9921	0.9855	0.9922	0.9888
AdaBoost Classifier	98.83	0.9923	0.9843	0.9923	0.9883
Gradient Boost Classifier	98.5	0.9965	0.9735	0.9966	0.9848
Voting (DT_LR_NB)	98.12	0.9964	0.9659	0.9965	0.9809
Stacking (DT_LR_NB)	98.08	0.9773	0.9843	0.9773	0.9808

Table 10: Training and Prediction Time for Ensemble Learning Models

Classifier	Training time (Sec)	Validation set prediction time (Sec)	Test set prediction time (Sec)
Bagging (bootstrap) 10 trees	13.2397	0.2908	0.2586
Bagging (bootstrap) 20 trees	12.8036	0.4289	0.3821
Bagging (bootstrap) 50 trees	23.8415	0.9719	0.8621
Bagging (bootstrap) 200 trees	119.1579	3.3392	4.0898
Bagging (bootstrap) 500 trees	316.3294	9.9717	7.2305
Stacking (ADA_RF_XGB)	199.6944	4.2528	4.6175
Random Forest Classifier	11.7664	0.8894	0.7479
Extra Trees Classifier	15.0623	2.8726	1.9418
Voting (ADA_RF_XGB)	36.0893	4.0067	3.4005
XGB Classifier	4.7058	0.2011	0.17
Cat-Boost Classifier	59.2789	0.2818	0.2159
Bagging (pasting)	33.6481	1.5804	1.4686
AdaBoost Classifier	95.9462	2.2985	2.3559
Gradient Boost Classifier	30.2445	0.2782	0.2199
Voting (DT_LR_NB)	25.742	0.6376	0.5627
Stacking (DT_LR_NB)	70.7991	0.1146	0.1459

Fig 6. Accuracy comparison for all models

Fig 7. Precision of all models

Fig 8. Recall of all models

Fig 9. Specificity of all models

Fig 10. F1-Score of all models

DISCUSSION

These findings demonstrate a significant correlation between the characteristics of URLs and their likelihood of being designated as malicious, underscoring the necessity of precise feature extraction for the efficacious identification of malevolent URLs. Furthermore, using well-preprocessed datasets leads to accurate classification results. Moreover, the precision and efficiency of the model in terms of classification or prediction are contingent upon the type and integrity of the data utilized. The selection of an appropriate model pertinent to the specific issue at hand is of paramount importance, as the correct model selection fosters accurate classifications and predictions at a high rate, resulting in the development of a reliable classifier. The results for traditional Machine Learning algorithms showed moderate accuracy. Most Machine Learning models, such as Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes, underperformed the proposed Ensemble models. This may be attributed to limitations such as overfitting or feature dependency in individual Machine Learning algorithms. The high accuracy achieved by deep learning

models stems from their ability to handle intricate relationships within the data, although the computation costs involved with training these complex models can be considerable. However, Ensemble Learning techniques consistently outperformed both individual Machine Learning and Deep Learning techniques. In particular, bagging with bootstrap sampling (Bagging (Bootstrap)) consistently exhibited exceptional accuracy while minimizing training and prediction times. The highest accuracy achieved was with Bagging (Bootstrap), which obtained 99.01%. This suggests that Bagging is the optimal approach for a real-time, practical system for malicious URL detection. Stacking demonstrated similar performance levels with slightly extended training durations due to its reliance on a structure consisting of several models. The proposed solution resulted in the following benefits of ensemble learning: Improved accuracy: By combining multiple models, ensemble learning often achieves significantly higher accuracy than individual learners. This is because each model learns from different aspects of the data, thus reducing bias and variance. Several studies

highlight the advantage of ensemble methods, including “Bagging Predictors” by Breiman (28), which shows significant improvement in accuracy and reduced variance compared to individual learners. Improved generalization: Ensemble learning often produces more robust models with improved generalization to unseen data, which helps mitigate overfitting. The article “Stacked Generalization” by Wolpert (27) improved the generalization ability of ensemble techniques, leading to better model performance on unseen data. Robustness to Noise and Outliers: Ensemble learning tends to be less sensitive to noise and outliers in the data, which increases model stability. The paper on “XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system” by Chen and Guestrin (29) emphasizes XGBoost’s robust handling of noise and outliers, which contributes to overall model stability. Increased Stability: By calculating average predictions from multiple models, ensemble learning generally produces more consistent results than individual models,

reducing variability in performance. Work on “Bagging Predictors” by Breiman (28) highlights how Bagging improves consistency by combining multiple predictions, reducing variability, and making models more stable. Reduce Complexity: While ensemble models may seem complex, they may sometimes simplify the learning process, especially when compared to complex deep learning, providing a better balance between accuracy and complexity. Some studies, such as “highly random trees” by Geurts et al. (30), have noted this advantage. Overall, these results, shown in Figure 11, strongly support the hypothesis that ensemble learning, and in particular Bagging (Bootstrap), is an effective technique for accurately detecting malicious URLs. It surpasses traditional machine learning algorithms in accuracy and performance, and demonstrates more favorable trade-offs between accuracy, computational complexity, and speed when compared to Deep Learning models.

Fig 11. Comparison of Accuracy, Training Time, and Prediction Time for all tested models.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study conducted a systematic evaluation of a range of machine learning, deep learning, and ensemble learning techniques for the purpose of detecting malicious URLs. Feature selection was employed, prioritizing those exhibiting the strongest correlation with the dependent variable, resulting in the selection of 13 lexical features from a total of 27 extracted from the dataset. The results demonstrate the superior performance of ensemble learning methods, specifically the Bagging (Bootstrap) technique, in achieving high accuracy alongside rapid training and prediction capabilities. This approach surpassed the accuracy of individual models and the speed of deep learning models, underscoring its effectiveness in mitigating the growing cybersecurity threat posed by malicious URLs. The speed and accuracy of the Bagging (Bootstrap) make it very useful for cybersecurity. It could be a strong tool in real-time systems for detecting and blocking threats.

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